

SUMS OF GENERALIZED HARMONIC SERIES

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Abstract

We prove two results on sums of generalized harmonic series.

1. Introduction

For nonnegative integers $a_1, a_2, \dots, a_k$ with $a_1 + \dots + a_k \geq 2$, define

$$H(a_1, a_2, \dots, a_k) = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{n^{a_1} (n+1)^{a_2} \dots (n+k-1)^{a_k}}. \quad (1)$$

It is easy to show that this series converges, and in fact (by considering the partial-fractions decomposition of $n^{-a_1} (n+1)^{-a_2} \dots (n+k-1)^{-a_k}$) that it can be written as a rational number plus a sum of values $\zeta(m)$ of the Riemann zeta function for $2 \leq m \leq \max\{a_1, \dots, a_k\}$. For example,

$$\begin{aligned} H(2, 3) &= \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{n^2 (n+1)^3} = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \left[-\frac{3}{n} + \frac{1}{n^2} + \frac{3}{n+1} + \frac{2}{(n+1)^2} + \frac{1}{(n+1)^3} \right] \\ &= -3 \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \left[\frac{1}{n} - \frac{1}{n+1} \right] + \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{n^2} + \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{2}{(n+1)^2} + \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{(n+1)^3} = -6 + 3\zeta(2) + \zeta(3). \end{aligned}$$

We call the quantity (1) an H -series of length k and weight $a_1 + \dots + a_k$. In §2 below we establish various formulas for H -series, in which Stirling numbers of the first kind are prominently involved. These are used in §3 to prove the following result.

Theorem 1. For any positive integers k, m with $m \geq 2$,

$$\sum_{a_1+a_2+\dots+a_k=m} H(a_1, \dots, a_k) = k\zeta(m),$$

where the sum is over k -tuples of nonnegative integers.

The H -series can be put into the framework of Shintani zeta functions [5]. For an $m \times k$ matrix $A = (a_{ij})$ and a k -vector $\vec{x} = (x_1, \dots, x_k)$, the Shintani zeta function of $(s_1, \dots, s_k)$ is

$$\zeta(s_1, \dots, s_k; A; \vec{x}) = \sum_{n_1, \dots, n_m \geq 0} \frac{1}{(x_1 + \sum_{i=1}^m a_{i1}n_i)^{s_1} \cdots (x_k + \sum_{i=1}^m a_{ik}n_i)^{s_k}}. \quad (2)$$

Then an H -series is just the special case of (2) with $m = 1$, $A = [1 \ 1 \ \cdots \ 1]$, and $\vec{x} = (1, 2, \dots, k)$. Several other special cases of Shintani zeta functions have been extensively studied. These include the Barnes zeta functions [1], which is the case $k = 1$; and the multiple zeta values [4, 7], which is the case where $m = k$, A is the $k \times k$ matrix with 1's on and below the main diagonal and 0's above, and $\vec{x} = (k, k - 1, \dots, 1)$. In the latter case the series (2) becomes

$$\begin{aligned} \zeta(s_1, \dots, s_k) &= \sum_{n_1, \dots, n_k \geq 0} \frac{1}{(k + \sum_{i=1}^k n_i)^{s_1} (k - 1 + \sum_{i=2}^k n_i)^{s_2} \cdots (1 + n_k)^{s_k}} \\ &= \sum_{m_1 > m_2 > \cdots > m_k \geq 1} \frac{1}{m_1^{s_1} m_2^{s_2} \cdots m_k^{s_k}}. \end{aligned}$$

In fact, Theorem 1 is superficially similar to the famous “sum conjecture” for multiple zeta values, i.e.,

$$\sum_{a_1+\dots+a_k=m, a_i \geq 1, a_1 > 1} \zeta(a_1, a_2, \dots, a_k) = \zeta(m) \quad (3)$$

for $m \geq 2$. The multiple zeta values sum conjecture (3) was made by the second author (see [4]), and was proved in full generality by A. Granville [2]. Note, however, that $\zeta(a_1, \dots, a_k)$ is a k -fold sum while $H(a_1, \dots, a_k)$ is a single sum. Also, the sum on the left-hand side of (3) is over k -tuples of positive integers rather than nonnegative integers.

It is also natural to ask about the sum of all H -series $H(a_1, \dots, a_k)$ of weight m over all k -tuples $(a_1, \dots, a_k)$ of positive integers of fixed weight. As indicated by the example

$$H(1, 1) = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{n(n+1)} = 1,$$

the answer is a rational number. More precisely, we have the following result, which follows easily from the machinery developed in §2.

Theorem 2. For $m \geq k \geq 2$,

$$\sum_{a_1+\dots+a_k=m, a_i \geq 1} H(a_1, \dots, a_k) = \frac{1}{(k-1)!} \sum_{i=0}^{k-2} \binom{k-2}{i} \frac{(-1)^i}{(i+1)^{m-k+1}}.$$

2. H -Series and Stirling Numbers of the First Kind

Henceforth we assume m to be a positive integer greater than 1. We have the following result.

Lemma 1. Let $1 \leq i < j \leq p$, and let $a_1, \dots, a_{i-1}, a_{i+1}, \dots, a_{j-1}, a_{j+1}, \dots, a_p$ be fixed nonnegative integers. Then

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{k=1}^{m-1} H(a_1, \dots, a_{i-1}, k, a_{i+1}, \dots, a_{j-1}, m-k, a_{j+1}, \dots, a_p) = \\ \frac{1}{j-i} [H(a_1, \dots, a_{i-1}, m-1, a_{i+1}, \dots, a_{j-1}, 0, a_{j+1}, \dots, a_p) - \\ H(a_1, \dots, a_{i-1}, 0, a_{i+1}, \dots, a_{j-1}, m-1, a_{j+1}, \dots, a_p)]. \end{aligned}$$

Proof. Evidently

$$\frac{1}{(n+i-1)(n+j-1)} = \frac{1}{j-i} \left[\frac{1}{n+i-1} - \frac{1}{n+j-1} \right],$$

so that

$$\begin{aligned} H(a_1, \dots, a_{i-1}, k, a_{i+1}, \dots, a_{j-1}, m-k, a_{j+1}, \dots, a_p) = \\ \frac{1}{j-i} [H(a_1, \dots, a_{i-1}, k, a_{i+1}, \dots, a_{j-1}, m-k-1, a_{j+1}, \dots, a_p) - \\ H(a_1, \dots, a_{i-1}, k-1, a_{i+1}, \dots, a_{j-1}, m-k, a_{j+1}, \dots, a_p)]. \end{aligned}$$

Now sum on k to obtain the conclusion. □

Using the preceding result, we can obtain a formula for the sum of all H -series of fixed weight and length having nonzero entries at specified locations.

Lemma 2. For $k \geq 1$ and $1 \leq i_0 < i_1 < \dots < i_k \leq n$,

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{a_{i_0}+a_{i_1}+\dots+a_{i_k}=m, a_j \neq 0 \text{ iff } j = i_q \text{ for some } q} H(a_1, \dots, a_n) = \\ \sum_{j=1}^k \frac{(-1)^{j-1} H_{i_0, i_{j-1}}^{(m-k)}}{(i_j - i_0)(i_j - i_1) \cdots (i_j - i_{j-1})(i_{j+1} - i_j) \cdots (i_k - i_j)}, \quad (4) \end{aligned}$$

where for $p \leq q$

$$H_{p,q}^{(n)} = \sum_{j=p}^q \frac{1}{j^n}.$$

Proof. For convenience, denote by $S(i_0, i_1, \dots, i_k; m)$ the left-hand side of equation (4). We proceed by induction on k , using Lemma 1. First, note that the case $k = 1$ of the result, i.e.,

$$S(i_0, i_1; m) = \frac{H_{i_0, i_1-1}^{(m-1)}}{i_1 - i_0},$$

follows immediately from Lemma 1. Now suppose the result holds for k , and consider $S(i_0, \dots, i_k, i_{k+1}; m)$, i.e., the sum of all $H(a_1, \dots, a_n)$ with nonzero entries $a_{i_0}, a_{i_1}, \dots, a_{i_{k+1}}$ adding up to m . Fix $a_{i_0}, \dots, a_{i_{k-1}}$, and sum the $H(a_1, \dots, a_n)$ from $a_{i_k} = 1$ to $a_{i_k} = m - a_{i_0} - \dots - a_{i_{k-1}} - 1$, keeping the sum of a_{i_k} and $a_{i_{k+1}}$ equal to $m - a_{i_0} - \dots - a_{i_k}$. By Lemma 1 this gives us, after summation on $a_{i_0}, \dots, a_{i_{k-1}}$,

$$\frac{1}{i_{k+1} - i_k} [S(i_0, \dots, i_{k-1}, i_k; m - 1) - S(i_0, \dots, i_{k-1}, i_{k+1}; m - 1)]. \quad (5)$$

By the induction hypothesis, $S(i_0, \dots, i_k; m - 1)$ is

$$\sum_{j=1}^{k-1} \frac{(-1)^{j-1} H_{i_0, i_j-1}^{(m-k-1)}}{(i_j - i_0) \cdots (i_j - i_{j-1})(i_{j+1} - i_j) \cdots (i_k - i_j)} + \frac{(-1)^{k-1} H_{i_0, i_k-1}^{(m-k-1)}}{(i_k - i_0) \cdots (i_k - i_{k-1})}$$

and $S(i_0, \dots, i_{k-1}, i_{k+1}; m - 1)$ is

$$\begin{aligned} & \sum_{j=1}^{k-1} \frac{(-1)^{j-1} H_{i_0, i_j-1}^{(m-k-1)}}{(i_j - i_0) \cdots (i_j - i_{j-1})(i_{j+1} - i_j) \cdots (i_{k-1} - i_j)(i_{k+1} - i_j)} \\ & + \frac{(-1)^{k-1} H_{i_0, i_{k+1}-1}^{(m-k-1)}}{(i_{k+1} - i_0) \cdots (i_{k+1} - i_{k-1})}. \end{aligned}$$

Hence the quantity (5) is

$$\begin{aligned} & \sum_{j=1}^{k-1} \frac{(-1)^{j-1} H_{i_0, i_j-1}^{(m-k-1)}}{(i_j - i_0) \cdots (i_j - i_{j-1})(i_{j+1} - i_j) \cdots (i_{k-1} - i_j)} \cdot \frac{\frac{1}{i_k - i_j} - \frac{1}{i_{k+1} - i_j}}{i_{k+1} - i_k} \\ & + \frac{(-1)^{k-1} H_{i_0, i_k-1}^{(m-k-1)}}{(i_k - i_0) \cdots (i_k - i_{k-1})(i_{k+1} - i_k)} + \frac{(-1)^k H_{i_0, i_{k+1}-1}^{(m-k-1)}}{(i_{k+1} - i_0) \cdots (i_{k+1} - i_{k-1})(i_{k+1} - i_k)} \\ & = \sum_{j=1}^{k+1} \frac{(-1)^{j-1} H_{i_0, i_j-1}^{(m-k-1)}}{(i_j - i_0) \cdots (i_j - i_{j-1})(i_{j+1} - i_j) \cdots (i_{k+1} - i_j)}. \end{aligned}$$

□

For $0 \leq k \leq n - 1$, let $C(k, n; m)$ be the sum of all $H(a_1, \dots, a_n)$ of weight m with exactly $k + 1$ of the a_i nonzero. Since each of the $H_{i_0, i_j - 1}^{(m-k)}$ in the preceding result is a sum of quantities $\frac{1}{p^{m-k}}$ with $1 \leq i_0 \leq p \leq i_j - 1 \leq n - 1$, for $k \geq 1$ we can write

$$C(k, n; m) = \sum_{j=1}^{n-1} \frac{c_{k,j}^{(n)}}{j^{m-k}} \tag{6}$$

where $c_{k,j}^{(n)}$ is rational. Then the numbers $c_{k,j}^{(n)}$ have a symmetry/antisymmetry property.

Lemma 3. For $1 \leq k, j \leq n - 1$, $c_{k,n-j}^{(n)} = (-1)^{k-1} c_{k,j}^{(n)}$.

Proof. Borrowing the notation used in the proof of Lemma 2, we have

$$C(k, n; m) = \sum_{1 \leq i_0 < i_1 < \dots < i_k \leq n} S(i_0, i_1, \dots, i_k; m).$$

Now note that Lemma 2 implies that if

$$S(i_0, i_1, \dots, i_k; m) = p_1 + p_2 \frac{1}{2^{m-k}} + \dots + p_{n-1} \frac{1}{(n-1)^{m-k}},$$

then

$$S(n+1-i_k, n+1-i_{k-1}, \dots, n+1-i_0; m) = (-1)^{k-1} \left(p_{n-1} + p_{n-2} \frac{1}{2^{m-k}} + \dots + p_1 \frac{1}{(n-1)^{m-k}} \right).$$

□

The first (and last) columns of the numbers $c_{k,j}^{(n)}$ can be written in terms of (unsigned) Stirling numbers of the first kind: we write $\left[\begin{smallmatrix} n \\ k \end{smallmatrix} \right]$ for the number of permutations of $\{1, 2, \dots, n\}$ with exactly k disjoint cycles. This notation follows [3], which is also a useful reference on these numbers.

Lemma 4. For $1 \leq k \leq n - 1$,

$$c_{k,1}^{(n)} = (-1)^{k-1} c_{k,n-1}^{(n)} = \frac{1}{(n-1)!} \left[\begin{smallmatrix} n \\ k+1 \end{smallmatrix} \right].$$

Proof. It suffices to prove the formula for $c_{k,n-1}^{(n)}$, as that for $c_{k,1}^{(n)}$ then follows from Lemma 3. Now Lemma 2 says that

$$c_{k,n-1}^{(n)} = \sum_{1 \leq i_0 < i_1 < \dots < i_{k-1} < n} \frac{(-1)^{k-1}}{(n-i_0)(n-i_1) \dots (n-i_{k-1})},$$

so to prove the result we need to show

$$\sum_{1 \leq i_0 < i_1 < \dots < i_{k-1} < n} \frac{(n-1)!}{(n-i_0)(n-i_1)\cdots(n-i_{k-1})} = \left[\begin{matrix} n \\ k+1 \end{matrix} \right].$$

The left-hand side is evidently the sum of all products of $n - k - 1$ distinct factors from the set $\{1, 2, \dots, n-1\}$, and that this is the Stirling number $\left[\begin{matrix} n \\ k+1 \end{matrix} \right]$ follows from consideration of the generating function

$$x(x+1)\cdots(x+n-1) = \sum_{k=1}^n \left[\begin{matrix} n \\ k \end{matrix} \right] x^k, \quad n \geq 1. \tag{7}$$

□

The preceding result generalizes as follows.

Lemma 5. For $1 \leq k, j \leq n - 1$,

$$c_{k,j}^{(n)} = \sum_{q=1}^j \sum_{p=1}^q \frac{(-1)^{p-1} \begin{bmatrix} q \\ p \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} n+1-q \\ k+2-p \end{bmatrix}}{(q-1)!(n-q)!}. \tag{8}$$

Proof. We need to show that

$$c_{k,j}^{(n)} - c_{k,j-1}^{(n)} = \sum_{p=1}^j \frac{(-1)^{p-1} \begin{bmatrix} j \\ p \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} n+1-j \\ k+2-p \end{bmatrix}}{(j-1)!(n-j)!}. \tag{9}$$

Suppose first that $j \leq k$. Using Lemma 2, all terms that contribute to $c_{k,n-j+1}^{(n)}$ also contribute to $c_{k,n-j}^{(n)}$, and the terms that contribute to $c_{k,n-j}^{(n)}$ and not to $c_{k,n-j+1}^{(n)}$ are of the forms

$$\frac{(-1)^{k-1} H_{i_0, n-j}^{(m-k)}}{(n+1-j-i_0)\cdots(n+1-j-i_{k-1})}, \quad i_0 < i_1 < \dots < i_{k-1} < n+1-j,$$

$$\frac{(-1)^{k-2} H_{i_0, n-j}^{(m-k)}}{(n+1-j-i_0)\cdots(n+1-j-i_{k-2})(i_k-n-1+j)},$$

$$i_0 < i_1 < \dots < i_{k-2} < n+1-j < i_k, \dots$$

$$\frac{(-1)^{k-j} H_{i_0, n-j}^{(m-k)}}{(n+1-j-i_0)\cdots(n+1-j-i_{k-j})(i_{k-j+2}-n-1+j)\cdots(i_k-n-1+j)},$$

$$i_0 < i_1 < \dots < i_{k-j} < n+1-j < i_{k-j+2} < \dots < i_k$$

(where we assume throughout that $i_0, \dots, i_k$ are integers between 1 and n), which

we refer to as classes $1, 2, \dots, j$. The contribution from class 1 is

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{i_0 < \dots < i_{k-1} < n+1-j} \frac{(-1)^{k-1}}{(n+1-j-i_0)(n+1-j-i_1) \cdots (n+1-j-i_{k-1})} \\ = (-1)^{k-1} \frac{\begin{bmatrix} n+1-j \\ k+1 \end{bmatrix}}{(n-j)!} = (-1)^{k-1} \frac{\begin{bmatrix} j \\ 1 \end{bmatrix}}{(j-1)!} \frac{\begin{bmatrix} n+1-j \\ k+1 \end{bmatrix}}{(n-j)!}. \end{aligned}$$

The contribution from class 2 is

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{n+1-j < i_k} \frac{1}{i_k - n - 1 + j} \sum_{i_0 < \dots < i_{k-2} < n+1-j} \frac{(-1)^{k-2}}{(n+1-j-i_0) \cdots (n+1-j-i_{k-2})} \\ = \sum_{s=1}^{j-1} \frac{1}{s} \sum_{i_0 < \dots < i_{k-2} < n+1-j} \frac{(-1)^{k-2}}{(n+1-j-i_0) \cdots (n+1-j-i_{k-2})} \\ = (-1)^{k-1} \frac{(-1) \begin{bmatrix} j \\ 2 \end{bmatrix}}{(j-1)!} \frac{\begin{bmatrix} n+1-j \\ k \end{bmatrix}}{(n-j)!}, \end{aligned}$$

and so forth. Note that for class j we must have $i_{k-j+2} = n+2-j, i_{k-j+3} = n+3-j, \dots, i_k = n$ and the contribution from this class is

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{i_0 < \dots < i_{k-j} < n+1-j} \frac{(-1)^{k-j}}{(n+1-j-i_0)(n+1-j-i_1) \cdots (n+1-j-i_{k-j})(j-1)!} \\ = (-1)^{k-1} \frac{(-1)^{j-1} \begin{bmatrix} j \\ j \end{bmatrix}}{(j-1)!} \frac{\begin{bmatrix} n+1-j \\ k-j+2 \end{bmatrix}}{(n-j)!}. \end{aligned}$$

Adding together the contributions, we see that $c_{k,n-j}^{(n)} - c_{k,n-j+1}^{(n)}$ is

$$(-1)^{k-1} \frac{\begin{bmatrix} j \\ 1 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} n+1-j \\ k+1 \end{bmatrix} - \begin{bmatrix} j \\ 2 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} n+1-j \\ k \end{bmatrix} + \dots + (-1)^{j-1} \begin{bmatrix} j \\ j \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} n+1-j \\ k-j+2 \end{bmatrix}}{(j-1)!(n-j)!}, \tag{10}$$

and equation (9) follows from Lemma 3.

Now if $j > k$, then classes $k+1, k+2, \dots, j$ are evidently empty. All the corresponding terms in (10) are zero, except for

$$(-1)^{k-1} \frac{(-1)^k \begin{bmatrix} j \\ k+1 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} n+1-j \\ 1 \end{bmatrix}}{(j-1)!(n-j)!} = -\frac{\begin{bmatrix} j \\ k+1 \end{bmatrix}}{(j-1)!}.$$

This quantity is accounted for by terms that contribute to $c_{k,n-j+1}^{(n)}$ and not to

$c_{k,n-j}^{(n)}$, provided

$$\sum_{n-j+1 < i_1 < \dots < i_k} \sum_{p=1}^k \frac{(-1)^{p-1}}{(i_p - n + j - 1)(i_p - i_1) \cdots (i_p - i_{p-1})(i_{p+1} - i_p) \cdots (i_k - i_p)} = \frac{\begin{bmatrix} j \\ k+1 \end{bmatrix}}{(j-1)!}. \quad (11)$$

By equating the expressions given for $c_{k,1}^{(j)}$ by Lemmas 2 and 4 respectively, we have

$$\sum_{1 < i_1 < \dots < i_k \leq j} \sum_{p=1}^k \frac{(-1)^{p-1}}{(i_p - 1)(i_p - i_1) \cdots (i_p - i_{p-1})(i_{p+1} - i_p) \cdots (i_k - i_p)} = \frac{\begin{bmatrix} j \\ k+1 \end{bmatrix}}{(j-1)!},$$

from which equation (11) follows. □

3. Proofs of the Theorems

First we need one more lemma.

Lemma 6. *For positive integers n and j ,*

$$\sum_{q=1}^j \binom{n+j-q}{j} \binom{j-1}{q-1} (-1)^q = -n. \quad (12)$$

Proof. We use the “snake oil method” of H. Wilf [6]. Let

$$F(x) = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} x^n \sum_{q=1}^j \binom{n+j-q}{j} \binom{j-1}{q-1} (-1)^q.$$

Then $F(x)$ can be rewritten

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{q=1}^j \binom{j-1}{q-1} (-1)^q \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \binom{n+j-q}{j} x^n &= \sum_{q=1}^j \binom{j-1}{q-1} (-1)^q \sum_{m=j}^{\infty} \binom{m}{j} x^{m-j+q} \\ &= \sum_{q=1}^j \binom{j-1}{q-1} (-1)^q \frac{x^q}{(1-x)^{j+1}} = \frac{-x}{(1-x)^{j+1}} \sum_{p=0}^{j-1} \binom{j-1}{p} (-x)^p \\ &= \frac{-x}{(1-x)^{j+1}} (1-x)^{j-1} = -\frac{x}{(1-x)^2} = -x - 2x^2 - 3x^3 - \dots, \end{aligned}$$

and equation (12) follows. □

Now we prove Theorems 1 and 2.

Proof of Theorem 1. We have

$$\sum_{a_1+a_2+\dots+a_n=m} H(a_1, \dots, a_n) = \sum_{k=0}^{n-1} C(k, n; m).$$

Now

$$\begin{aligned} C(0, n; m) &= H(m, 0, 0, \dots, 0) + H(0, m, 0, \dots, 0) + \dots + H(0, \dots, 0, m) \\ &= \zeta(m) + \zeta(m) - 1 + \dots + \zeta(m) - 1 - \frac{1}{2^m} - \dots - \frac{1}{(n-1)^m} \\ &= n\zeta(m) - (n-1) - \frac{n-2}{2^m} - \dots - \frac{1}{(n-1)^m} \end{aligned}$$

and

$$C(k, n; m) = \sum_{j=1}^{n-1} \frac{c_{k,j}^{(n)}}{j^{m-k}}, \quad k \geq 1,$$

so to prove the result we need

$$\sum_{i=1}^{n-1} j^i c_{i,j}^{(n)} = n - j$$

for all $1 \leq j \leq n - 1$. By Lemma 5 this means we must show

$$\sum_{i=1}^{n-1} \sum_{q=1}^j \sum_{p=1}^q j^i \frac{(-1)^{p-1} \binom{q}{p} \binom{n+1-q}{i+2-p}}{(q-1)!(n-q)!} = n - j. \tag{13}$$

We rewrite the left-hand side of equation (13) as

$$\sum_{q=1}^j \sum_{p=1}^q \frac{(-1)^{p-1} \binom{q}{p}}{(q-1)!} \cdot \frac{1}{(n-q)!} \sum_{i=1}^{n-1} \binom{n+1-q}{i+2-p} j^i. \tag{14}$$

If $p = 1$, the inner sum in (14) is

$$\sum_{i=1}^{n-1} \binom{n+1-q}{i+1} j^i = \sum_{i=2}^n \binom{n+1-q}{i} j^{i-1} = \frac{(n+j-q)!}{j(j-1)!} - \binom{n+1-q}{1},$$

where we have used equation (7). Hence

$$\frac{1}{(n-q)!} \sum_{i=1}^{n-1} \binom{n+1-q}{i+1} j^i = \binom{n+j-q}{j} - 1$$

since $\binom{n+1-q}{1} = (n-q)!$. If $p \geq 2$, then the inner sum in (14) is

$$\sum_{i=1}^{n-1} \binom{n+1-q}{i+2-p} j^i = \sum_{i \geq 1} \binom{n+1-q}{i} j^{i+p-2} = j^{p-2} \frac{(n+j-q)!}{(j-1)!} = j^{p-1} \frac{(n+j-q)!}{j!},$$

again using equation (7), from which follows

$$\frac{1}{(n-q)!} \sum_{i=1}^{n-1} \begin{bmatrix} n+1-q \\ i+2-p \end{bmatrix} j^i = j^{p-1} \binom{n+j-q}{j}.$$

Thus, the sum (14) can be written

$$\begin{aligned} & \sum_{q=1}^j \left[\binom{n+j-q}{j} - 1 \right] + \sum_{q=2}^j \sum_{p=2}^q \frac{(-1)^{p-1} \begin{bmatrix} q \\ p \end{bmatrix}}{(q-1)!} \binom{n+j-q}{j} j^{p-1} \\ &= -j + \sum_{q=1}^j \binom{n+j-q}{j} + \sum_{q=2}^j \binom{n+j-q}{j} \frac{1}{(q-1)!} \sum_{p=2}^q (-j)^{p-1} \begin{bmatrix} q \\ p \end{bmatrix}. \end{aligned}$$

If we use equation (7), this becomes

$$\begin{aligned} & -j + \sum_{q=1}^j \binom{n+j-q}{j} + \sum_{q=2}^j \binom{n+j-q}{j} \frac{1}{(q-1)!} \left[(1-j) \cdots (q-1-j) - \begin{bmatrix} q \\ 1 \end{bmatrix} \right] \\ &= -j + \sum_{q=1}^j \binom{n+j-q}{j} - \sum_{q=2}^j \binom{n+j-q}{j} + \sum_{q=2}^j \binom{n+j-q}{j} \binom{j-1}{q-1} (-1)^{q-1} \\ &= -j + \binom{n+j-1}{j} + \sum_{q=2}^j \binom{n+j-q}{j} \binom{j-1}{q-1} (-1)^{q-1} \\ &= -j - \sum_{q=1}^j \binom{n+j-q}{j} \binom{j-1}{q-1} (-1)^q. \end{aligned}$$

Then equation (13) follows from Lemma 6. □

Proof of Theorem 2. It suffices to show that

$$c_{n-1,j}^{(n)} = \frac{(-1)^{j-1}}{(n-1)!} \binom{n-2}{j-1}.$$

From Lemma 5 we have

$$\begin{aligned} c_{n-1,j}^{(n)} &= \sum_{q=1}^j \sum_{p=1}^q \frac{(-1)^{p-1} \begin{bmatrix} q \\ p \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} n+1-q \\ n+1-p \end{bmatrix}}{(q-1)!(n-q)!} = \sum_{q=1}^j \frac{(-1)^{q-1} \begin{bmatrix} q \\ q \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} n+1-q \\ n+1-q \end{bmatrix}}{(q-1)!(n-q)!} \\ &= \frac{1}{(n-1)!} \sum_{q=1}^j (-1)^{q-1} \binom{n-1}{q-1} = \frac{(-1)^{j-1}}{(n-1)!} \binom{n-2}{j-1}. \end{aligned}$$

□

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